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NAUTILOS

Report on communication activities at key events

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NAUTILOS - New Approach to Underwater Technologies for Innovative, Low-cost Ocean observation is an H2020 project funded under the Future of Seas and Oceans Flagship Initiative, coordinated by the National Research Council of Italy (CNR, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche). It brings together a group of 21 entities from 11 European countries with multidisciplinary expertise ranging from ocean instrumentation development and integration, ocean sensing and sampling instrumentation, data processing, modelling and control, operational oceanography and biology and ecosystems and biogeochemistry such, water and climate change science, technological marine applications and research infrastructures.

NAUTILOS will fill-in marine observation and modelling gaps for chemical, biological and deep ocean physics variables through the development of a new generation of cost-effective sensors and samplers, the integration of the aforementioned technologies within observing platforms and their deployment in large-scale demonstrations in European seas. The fundamental aim of the project will be to complement and expand current European observation tools and services, to obtain a collection of data at a much higher spatial resolution, temporal regularity and length than currently available at the European scale, and to further enable and democratise the monitoring of the marine environment to both traditional and non-traditional data users.

NAUTILOS is one of two projects included in the EU's efforts to support of the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy by supporting the demonstration of new and innovative technologies to measure the Essential Ocean Variables (EOV).

More information on the project can be found at: <https://www.NAUTILOS-h2020.eu>.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	4
COPYRIGHT	4
TABLE OF CONTENTS	5
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS	7
I. INTRODUCTION	8
1.1. The importance of attending key events to support policy making	8
1.2. Related documents	9
II. NAUTILOS KEY EVENTS ATTENDED	11
2.1. 9th EuroGOOS International Conference; Online, 3-5 May 2021	11
2.2. EMODnet Second Open Conference and Jamboree; Online, 14 -16 June 2021	12
2.3. EMODnet Ingestion annual meeting; Online, 29 October 2021	13
2.4. International Ocean Data Conference 2022; Hybrid - Sopot, Poland 14-16 February 2022	13
2.5. European Maritime Day - Ocean observations and marine data in support of the EU Green Deal; Hybrid – Ravenna, Italy, 19 -10 May 2022	15
2.6. Ocean Data Week - Low cost technologies for ocean data monitoring and participatory actions; Hybrid – Genova, Italy, 27-30 June 2023.....	16
2.7. 10 years of the Galway Statement. Celebrating a decade of marine research - Wake-up pitches from ongoing projects; Hybrid – Galway, Ireland, 5-6 July 2023	17
III. KEY EVENT ORGANIZED BY NAUTILOS	18
3.1. European Maritime Day – Citizens Empowerment Through Ocean Knowledge Co- Production; Hybrid – Ravenna, Italy, 19 -10 May 2022	18
3.2. NAUTILOS Policy Round Table; Hybrid – Genova, Italy, 27 June 2023.....	19
IV. CONCLUSIONS	20

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 10.6 underscores NAUTILOS' active participation in significant policy-engagement events, which build upon the foundational policies outlined in Deliverable 10.5 within the NAUTILOS project. NAUTILOS has taken a proactive role in various events, including EMODNET, European Maritime Day, EuroGOOS, and a policy round table organised by NAUTILOS itself. The intended audience of these initiatives encompasses a wide range of stakeholders, such as National bodies, the European Commission (EC), Parliamentary bodies, officials from Member States (MS), United Nations (UN) entities, as well as HELCOM and OSPAR commissions.

The overarching objective of these endeavours is to amplify the awareness among policy makers about the critical necessity of advancing novel technologies and harnessing existing scientific knowledge to enhance our comprehension of the cumulative impact influencing the well-being of our ocean. Furthermore, these efforts highlight the significance of instituting and supporting long-term initiatives in ocean observation. By doing so, we can gather consistent and reliable data over extended periods, enabling a more comprehensive understanding of ocean dynamics and changes, which in turn will contribute to informed decision-making and policy formulation for the sustainable management of our marine resources and ecosystems.

LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AtlantECO	Atlantic ECOSystems assessment, forecasting & sustainability
Blue-Cloud	Piloting innovative services for Marine Research & the Blue Economy
CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics
DG MARE	Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries
DOOS	European component of the Global Ocean Observing System of the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO
EC	European Commission
EMODNET	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EOVs	Essential Ocean Variables
EU	European Union
EUROFLEETS+	An Alliance of European marine research infrastructure to meet the evolving needs of the research and industrial communities
EuroGOOS	European Global Ocean Observing System
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
G7	Group of Seven
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
HELCOM	Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission
iAtlantic	Integrated Assessment of Atlantic Marine Ecosystems in Space and Time
IOC	Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission
IODE	International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange
MS	Member States
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive.
NAUTILOS	New Approach to Underwater Technologies for Innovative, Low-cost Ocean observation
ODYSSEA	Operating a Network of Integrated Observatory Systems in the Mediterranean Sea
OSPAR	Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic
R&D	Research and Development
RTD – DG	Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
UN	United Nations
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization
WOC	World Ocean Council

I. INTRODUCTION

NAUTILOS assumes a pivotal role in advancing policy areas by virtue of its comprehensive approach to marine observation and data collection. Through concerted efforts, NAUTILOS is developing, validating, and testing in various scenarios an array of 11 sensor types and 2 sampler types to enhance the observation of the marine environment. This undertaking is poised to foster heightened integration of observations derived from diverse platforms, presenting a monumental step towards more informed and effective policymaking. By tackling the challenge of observing 14 biogeochemistry, and biology and ecosystems Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) as defined by the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS), as well as 2 deep ocean-specific EOVs specified by the Deep Ocean Observing Strategy (DOOS) and 9 Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) Descriptors, NAUTILOS addresses critical gaps in data availability. Notably, these developments align seamlessly with the imperatives of global and EU initiatives, programs, and legislation, as evidenced by the project's early alignment with political and societal requirements through deliverable 2.1.

The far-reaching significance of NAUTILOS extends to domains such as the Common Fisheries Policy (EU REGULATION 1380/2013) and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (Directive 2008/56/EC). In direct alignment with the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO and the United Nations' Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, NAUTILOS undertakes research and development priorities that resonate deeply with the overarching goals of enhancing ocean science and sustainability. This encompasses a multifaceted approach about R&D Priority Areas 3, 4, 6, and 7, where the project's impact is reflected in ocean-system observation, research, prediction, data systems, and policy considerations. By adhering to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles and ensuring the open accessibility of its scientific data, NAUTILOS is positioned to leave a lasting legacy that aligns harmoniously with the UN Decade's aspirations.

Vital to the achieving of the broader objective of sustainable development and responsible ocean use (SDG 14) is an enhanced understanding of the marine system, which hinges crucially on robust marine observation efforts. NAUTILOS recognises that the pressing issues encapsulated in SDG 14, ranging from ocean acidification and marine pollution to resource management and scientific advancement, demand collective solutions that span developed and developing nations alike. This collective ethos resonates in the project's direct orientation with multiple SDG 14 targets: from mitigating marine pollution (14.1) and adopting ecosystem-based approaches (14.2) to addressing ocean acidification (14.3), enhancing research capacity (14.A), and formulating policies for ocean conservation and sustainable resource use (14.C). By providing access to pertinent, high-quality data, NAUTILOS plays a pivotal role in empowering sustainable ocean management and utilisation, underpinning the achievement of SDG 14's objectives.

1.1. The importance of attending key events to support policy making

The attendance of targeted events to disseminate the policy interests of NAUTILOS holds immense importance in ensuring the project's impact by reaching a broader audience and influencing the formulation of effective policies. These events provide a platform for NAUTILOS to showcase its research findings, technological advancements, and policy-relevant outcomes to key stakeholders, policymakers, experts, and the general public. A deeper exploration of the significance of participating in such events is proposed below:

Knowledge Dissemination and Awareness: Specific events, such as EMODNET, European Maritime Day, EuroGOOS, and policy round tables, draw participants from various sectors related to marine and ocean affairs. These gatherings serve as knowledge hubs where NAUTILOS can share its insights, methodologies, and innovative technologies with policymakers and experts who have a direct

influence on shaping marine policies. By actively participating in these events, NAUTILOS can raise awareness about the significance of its observations, data, and research outcomes, fostering a deeper understanding of the project's contribution.

Networking and Collaboration: Attending targeted events facilitates networking opportunities with other projects, initiatives, organisations, and individuals with shared interests. These interactions can lead to collaboration opportunities, where NAUTILOS can accord its policy interests with other stakeholders to collectively address marine challenges. Collaboration can enhance the project's credibility, amplify its impact, and broaden its reach across diverse sectors. Moreover, these interactions can help NAUTILOS gather feedback, insights, and perspectives from a range of stakeholders, enriching its policy recommendations and ensuring they are well-rounded and applicable.

Policy Influence and Adoption: Specific events often attract decision makers, government officials, and representatives from international organisations. By engaging with these influential stakeholders, NAUTILOS can directly influence the political discourse and advocate for the incorporation of its findings and recommendations into policy frameworks. Presenting concrete evidence, data, and success stories from the project can enhance the credibility of NAUTILOS' policy interests, making them more likely to be considered and integrated into legislative and regulatory processes.

Tailored Messaging and Advocacy: Different events may have specific themes, audiences, and contexts. By participating in various events, NAUTILOS can tailor its messaging and advocacy efforts to resonate with the priorities of each audience. This customised approach ensures that policymakers and stakeholders perceive NAUTILOS' work as directly relevant to their specific areas of interest, increasing the likelihood of policy uptake and implementation.

Public Engagement and Transparency: Beyond policymakers, these events attract media, educators, students, and the general public interested in marine issues. By participating, NAUTILOS can foster public engagement, promote transparency, and share its accomplishments and contributions with a wider audience. This helps build public support for marine conservation efforts and encourages the dissemination of accurate information about the project's goals and impact.

Importance of Ocean Observation: NAUTILOS' involvement in these events underscores the critical role of ocean observation in advancing our understanding of marine ecosystems, resource management, and environmental health. By showcasing its advancements in sensor technology and data collection methodologies, NAUTILOS contributes to the larger conversation on the value of sustained, comprehensive ocean observation efforts. This advocacy for ocean observation reinforces the importance of informed decision-making based on reliable and up-to-date data.

Democratisation of Science: With its participation in events involving a multitude of target audiences, NAUTILOS promotes the democratisation of science and research by openly sharing findings and engaging with policymakers, experts, and the public. This creates an inclusive dialogue that breaks down barriers, prejudice and misunderstanding between scientific research and broader society. The approach fosters a sense of ownership and collaboration, encouraging individuals from various backgrounds to participate in addressing complex marine challenges.

1.2. Related documents

D2.1. A review and prospectus of the mandate for marine environmental monitoring systems: technology challenges and opportunities

This report compiles the outcomes of the work performed in Task 2.1 (Political and societal drivers and requirements), informing on the potential of evolving trends in technological progress for advancing contemporary marine environmental monitoring practices and examining the role any resulting changes in established operating paradigms could play in shaping the socio-political framework defining ocean observation needs, at global and European level.

D10.1. Outreach, Communication and Dissemination Strategy

Report outlining the communication and dissemination strategy and actions that are planned to be implemented throughout the project's lifetime in order to achieve the project's widest promotion, greatest visibility and awareness to the external audiences with a particular emphasis on citizen science campaigns. The Communication and Dissemination Plan provides the framework and structure of project's information, communication and activities. Additionally, it defines the communication goals, objectives and timelines and allocates responsibilities at partner level. Lastly, it features a set of key performance indicators (KPIs) for the quantification and measurement of the communication and dissemination activities' success.

D10.3 Policy Briefs

Deliverable 10.3 builds on NAUTILOS project's policy foundation from Deliverable 10.5, presenting three policy briefs focused on different areas. The first brief emphasizes citizen science for marine observation, enhancing sustainability. The second one underscores ocean observation's role in the understanding of the climate change, urging ongoing support and integration. The third, highlights ocean observation's economic importance and sustainable resource management through international cooperation.

Two of the briefs were shared at the Ocean Race Grand Finale, reaching policymakers. The final brief's public launch will be during NAUTILOS' concluding conference and aims to broaden its impact and reverberations long after the project's end. NAUTILOS seeks to advance ocean knowledge, sustainability, and policy engagement for responsible global ocean governance.

D10.5 Strategic Policy Agenda

This report frames the strategic policy agenda for the NAUTILOS project and outlines communication priorities towards policy makers that include National bodies, EC, Parliaments, UN bodies, HELCOM and OSPAR commissions. It takes into account EU and International policies such as the SDGs and the Ocean Investment Platform from the World Ocean Council (WOC), and key initiatives promoted by the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) such as The UN International Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development which aims to raise public awareness of the urgent need to promote new technologies and the use of existing science to increase our understanding of the cumulative impact that affects our ocean.

D10.8. Outreach, Communication and Dissemination Strategy

An updated version of deliverable 10.1 issued in September 2022.

II. NAUTILOS KEY EVENTS ATTENDED

2.1. 9th EuroGOOS International Conference; Online, 3-5 May 2021

The 9th EuroGOOS International Conference, themed "Advances in Operational Oceanography: Expanding Europe's Ocean Observing and Forecasting Capacity," was conducted against a backdrop of significant developments in the field of oceanography. These developments, observed in recent years, particularly pertained to the bolstered networking and collaboration within ocean observation, modeling, data management, and the provision of ocean-related services to society. It is worth noting that this conference occurred in 2021, marking the commencement of the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development.

During this time frame, the G7 Working Group on the Future of Seas and Oceans made a pivotal statement underscoring the paramount importance of ocean observation and monitoring activities. This statement also heralded the establishment of a Coordination Centre dedicated to ocean affairs. The strategic framework of this working group drew heavily from the 2030 Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) strategy, aimed at contributing to the realisation of the UN Sustainable Development Goals. This strategic blueprint laid the groundwork for envisioning a comprehensively integrated global system, spanning from the open ocean to coastal regions and from surface waters to ocean depths. This integrated system was envisioned as pivotal in collating essential information required for sustainable development, security, well-being, and prosperity, with a special focus on climate change, operational services, and ocean health.

The NAUTILOS project received significant prominence at the 9th EuroGOOS International Conference, as it was presented by NAUTILOS project Coordinator both the presentation and its accompanying abstract are readily available [here](#).

Furthermore, the comprehensive proceedings of the 9th EuroGOOS International Conference, titled "Advances in Operational Oceanography: Expanding Europe's Ocean Observing and Forecasting Capacity," have been made permanently available on the conference's [official website](#).

In 2021, a momentous initiative took centre stage: the launch of the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development. This marked a pivotal juncture in the journey of EMODnet, a distinguished European marine data and knowledge service and intermediary. Notably, EMODnet had already achieved a significant milestone in 2019 when it completed its inaugural decade of operation. In 2020, EMODnet celebrated this impressive milestone through a commemorative 10-year anniversary webinar. This webinar served as an illustrious platform to showcase EMODnet's remarkable decade-long journey, spotlighting a decade of progress, the formation of numerous partnerships, and the attainment of notable achievements during the preceding ten years. The EMODnet Open Conference of 2021, accompanied by its collaborative partner event, the Jamboree, was meticulously designed to capitalise on this rising wave of enthusiasm. It convened a diverse spectrum of stakeholders, drawing participants not only from within the EMODnet partnership but also extending its reach beyond those boundaries. The primary objectives of this multifaceted gathering included:

- Celebrating and placing a spotlight on a decade of remarkable progress achieved across the expansive EMODnet network.
- Recognising and nurturing both established and burgeoning partnerships, both within Europe and on a global scale.
- Actively seeking input from the user community, eliciting insights into the value of EMODnet's data, data products, and services, with a specific emphasis on enhancing the user experience.
- Responsively collecting stakeholder feedback, an essential component in shaping the future course of EMODnet and delineating its vision through 2030.

The Jamboree, thoughtfully synchronised with the main conference, offered a moment for celebration, as it allowed participants to revel in the achievements of EMOD-network's core delivery partners. Additionally, it facilitated exploration of strategies for transitioning towards a harmonised approach. This approach aimed to make all data and data products seamlessly accessible, conspicuously visible, and effortlessly downloadable through the central EMODnet portal.

Within the dynamic context of the NAUTILOS project, a significant milestone was achieved with the acceptance of a presentation and poster. The project coordinator's presentation was thoughtfully scheduled for Session 5: Ocean Observing & Data Collection, and his pitch can be found [here](#).

Furthermore, one of our project partners, NIVA, made a substantive and impactful contribution during the EMODnet Jamboree event. Their focus was on the critical domain of Citizen Science, and their active participation extended to both a concise 5-minute presentation and influential engagement in a panel discussion. A comprehensive reference to their role and involvement can be found in the draft agenda, accessible [here](#).

2.3. EMODnet Ingestion annual meeting; Online, 29 October 2021

The EMODnet Data Ingestion portal has a twofold mission. Firstly, it aims to identify and engage with potential data providers who can enrich the existing data offerings. This encompasses historical datasets that could augment the extensive European archives, serving a multitude of applications. Additionally, it involves real-time data streams from operational oceanography monitoring platforms, which can be integrated into the European operational oceanography data exchange system. This integration is crucial for fueling forecasting models and supporting various operational activities.

The portal's core objective is to streamline the data ingestion process. This means that data holders, whether from the public or private sectors, who are not yet connected to established marine data management infrastructures, can effortlessly release their data for secure storage and subsequent dissemination through EMODnet. This collaborative effort enhances the overall dataset accessibility for a wide range of users, aligning with EMODnet's principle of "collect data once and use it many times."

During the EMODnet Ingestion Annual Assembly meeting in 2021, there was a presentation on how NAUTILOS could play a pivotal role in supporting and facilitating data transfer within the broader framework of the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet). ETT, a partner in both NAUTILOS and EMODnet Ingestion, highlighted that NAUTILOS has the potential to collaborate with EMODnet Data Ingestion, which focuses on simplifying the process for new and potential data providers to ingest their marine datasets. These datasets can then be further processed, published as open data, and contribute to applications beneficial for society. One specific role that NAUTILOS could fulfill is establishing a machine-to-machine transfer of Near Real-Time (NRT) data from monitoring stations, effectively making it a public service.

These opportunities for collaboration align seamlessly with NAUTILOS's primary objectives, particularly in expanding the scope of European observational tools and services. Moreover, this collaboration aims to democratize the monitoring of the marine environment, making it accessible to both traditional and non-traditional data users. More information available [here](#)

2.4. International Ocean Data Conference 2022; Hybrid - Sopot, Poland 14-16 February 2022

The International Ocean Data Conference occurred in Sopot, Poland, from February 14 to February 16, 2022, adopting a hybrid format with 590 online and 60 on-site participants. This event was a collaborative effort organised by the Government of Poland, specifically through the Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences, in conjunction with the IODE Programme of the IOC and the Decade Coordination Unit. Its primary objectives encompassed examining regional and global strategies and policies necessary for establishing a digital ecosystem, deliberating on current and anticipated technological advancements and their practical implementation, and identifying prospective pathways in ocean data and information management. These objectives were set within the broader framework of the UN Ocean Decade's multi-sectoral vision.

Throughout the conference, the global community focused on ocean data and information management collectively generated significant recommendations, including:

- The imperative need for heightened efforts in standardisation, best practices, harmonisation, and the wider application of FAIR and CARE principles.
- The importance of expanding community engagement, incorporating citizen science, indigenous knowledge, and enhancing data literacy.
- The necessity to intensify endeavors in global data and information system interoperability and networking, ultimately striving to establish a global ocean digital commons and data ecosystem. This involves the interconnection and integration of data systems (digital twins) from diverse disciplines and sectors, including the private sector, related to the ocean.
- The promotion of integrated multi-hazard warning systems within Earth System Observation, Research, and Prediction programs, with a focus not only on ocean health but also on realising the UN Ocean Decade's societal outcomes, emphasising the ocean's qualities and its impact on people's lives.

Within the framework of the UN Ocean Decade, the global ocean data and marine value chain community collaboratively worked toward creating a dynamic ocean digital ecosystem, with key features:

- Full traceability of data provenance, achieved through a standardized set of metadata enriched with thematic, sector-specific, and relevance information (e.g., to EOVs, SDGs).
- A fully machine-searchable and actionable ocean digital ecosystem, ensuring that when data or metadata are updated, they automatically flow seamlessly through the data pipeline and are accessible via the global digital commons.

NAUTILOS made a valuable contribution to the conference by providing a pre-recorded presentation on the project's objectives and anticipated impacts, which can be viewed here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OZ7ZnZFSCsE>

2.5. European Maritime Day - Ocean observations and marine data in support of the EU Green Deal; Hybrid – Ravenna, Italy, 19 -10 May 2022

EuroSea, Blue-Cloud, and EMODnet conducted a joint workshop on May 19th, during the European Maritime Day, titled "Ocean observations, marine data, and services for the European Green Deal."

Setting the stage for this workshop, more than 80 individuals, both present in the room and connecting via Zoom, gathered to hear from a distinguished lineup of speakers. These speakers not only showcased successful instances of collaboration across projects but also engaged in discussions about the path forward. EuroSea presented the priorities and recommendations highlighted in a joint policy brief produced in collaboration with Blue-Cloud and other EU projects like NAUTILOS, EUROFLEETS+, iAtlantic, ODYSSEA, and AtlantECO. This collaborative effort was facilitated by the EC-funded Horizon Results Booster and contributed to the broader collaboration within the All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance.

The Policy Brief put forward five key recommendations aimed at enhancing the connections between the Blue Economy and ocean knowledge:

- Establish a European Policy Framework for Sustained Funding of Scientific Ocean Observations.
- Support the Professional Growth of the Next Generation of 'Blue Staff.'
- Harness the Power of Data by Investing in IT Observations.
- Define Global Standards and Practices for Interoperability.
- Strengthen Citizen Science for Policy Impact, Equitable Access, Democratisation, and Essential Data Contributions.

The workshop delved into the significance of a well-coordinated, enduring, and fit-for-purpose ocean observation and information system that serves the needs of policy, industry, and society at large. Experts and participants engaged in discussions on potential avenues to achieve this goal, including European framework and national commitments, an effective science-policy interface, and the promotion of public-private partnerships. The workshop also cast a forward-looking gaze upon the opportunities, gaps, and priorities necessary to fulfill the objectives of the European Green Deal.

2.6. Ocean Data Week - Low cost technologies for ocean data monitoring and participatory actions; Hybrid – Genova, Italy, 27-30 June 2023

The poster features a dark teal background. At the top left, there are two logos: 'ETT GENOVA SUPPORTER' and 'THE OCEAN RACE GENOVA THE GRAND FINALE 27-30 JUNE 2023'. The main text is centered and reads: 'We Race with the Future' in a smaller font, followed by 'Low cost / cost effective technologies for ocean data monitoring and participatory actions' in a large, bold, white font. Below this, the time 'h. 10.30/13.00 - 14.30/17.00' is displayed. At the bottom, a yellow rectangular box contains the text 'FRIDAY 30/06/2023'.

Against the backdrop of the renowned World Ocean Race, a week-long series of talks and workshops addressing critical themes related to sustainability, the blue economy, smart cities, and citizen science unfolded in Genova from June 27th to June 30th, 2023, organised by ETT. This dedicated week provided a tangible platform for the exchange of ideas and knowledge among Europe's most influential figures in the sustainability arena. It actively contributed to the global discourse on ocean preservation and sustainable development.

Acknowledging the indispensable role of the ocean in Earth's ecosystem is pivotal for its sustainable stewardship and responsible utilisation. A full day was dedicated to the exploration of "Low-Cost/Cost-Effective Technologies for Ocean Data Monitoring and Participatory Initiatives," underscoring the

significance of not confining ocean observation exclusively to experts and scientists. Citizen science offers a collaborative paradigm wherein the general public participates in scientific research projects, contributing valuable data and observations for researchers to analyse.

Furthermore, it emphasised that endorsing and bolstering citizen science initiatives offers policymakers the prospect of democratising marine observation science. This heralds an innovative, self-driven, sustainable, and cost-effective observatory model. Such an approach not only empowers individuals but also facilitates well-informed decision-making founded on the most reliable and comprehensive information available. Recognising this critical importance, NAUTILOS unveiled a policy brief titled "[Empowering Citizens Through Ocean Knowledge Co-production](#)".

Moreover, within the same session, the NAUTILOS Technology Innovation Board Manager delivered a presentation on the animal tagging system.

This session was organised in collaboration with the Chamber of Commerce of Genova and the Enterprise Europe Network, offering attendees an opportunity to engage in a transnational B2B Ocean Race event where the NAUTILOS TIB manager also participated.

The full session is available here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BhUrZbOzL8g>.

2.7. 10 years of the Galway Statement. Celebrating a decade of marine research - Wake-up pitches from ongoing projects; Hybrid – Galway, Ireland, 5-6 July 2023

Co-organized by the Irish Government, the European Commission, the Marine Institute, and the University of Galway, the hybrid event titled "2013 – 2023: A Decade of the Galway Statement – Celebrating Ten Years of Collaborative Marine Research Across the Atlantic Ocean – Our Shared Resource" was held on July 5-6, 2023, in Galway, Ireland.

The Galway Statement, which was signed in 2013 by Canada, the European Union, and the United States of America, marked a significant milestone in the realm of marine research cooperation across the Atlantic. Since then, over a thousand research teams have been dedicated to mapping the seabed of the North Atlantic, making groundbreaking discoveries of new species, conducting studies on the impact of climate change on biodiversity, establishing a network of floating universities, and much more.

These achievements ultimately paved the way for a new era of ocean-scale cooperation, culminating in the signing of the All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance Declaration in July 2022.

This event brought together European and international partners and stakeholders from the Atlantic region. It served not only as a commemoration of past accomplishments but also as a steppingstone towards the 2023 All-Atlantic Forum in South Africa.

During this event, NAUTILOS was presented in the wake-up pitch session by the project coordinator. He highlighted the project's objectives and expected impacts, which you can view in the presentation linked [here](#).

III. KEY EVENT ORGANIZED BY NAUTILOS

- 3.1. European Maritime Day – Citizens Empowerment Through Ocean Knowledge Co- Production; Hybrid – Ravenna, Italy, 19 -10 May 2022

The eagerly awaited European Maritime Day 2022 unfolded in Ravenna, Italy, on May 19-20, adopting a hybrid format that seamlessly integrated both physical and remote participation. It assembled a diverse congregation, with 850 individuals physically present and an additional 600 participants connecting remotely from various European locations. This event marked a significant milestone in the rejuvenation of face-to-face interactions and the cultivation of collaborative endeavours within the maritime community.

In collaboration with Lega Navale, Outdoor Portofino, Surfrider Foundation, and the University of Bologna, NAUTILOS co-hosted an EU4Ocean workshop as part of the European Maritime Day event.

The primary focus of this workshop was to facilitate the exchange of experiences, noteworthy accomplishments, and exemplary practices derived from diverse citizen science projects. The workshop outlined specific objectives, which encompassed:

- Championing the adoption, exploration, and promotion of best practices within Citizen Science (CS) projects, with an eye toward the future.

- Engaging participants and the EU4Ocean Coalition audience to pinpoint opportunities for collaborative co-creation.
- Delving into the existing gaps and requisites that bridge the realms of Science, Policy, and Citizens.
- Paving the way for the expansion and advancement of Citizen Science projects.

To accomplish these objectives, the workshop actively engaged panelists, the audience, and other invited participants. The dialogues and insights shared during the workshop were enriched by drawing upon their collective experiences in the domain of citizen science activities and initiatives.

To see the full session: <https://player.vimeo.com/video/714116804>

3.2. NAUTILOS Policy Round Table; Hybrid – Genova, Italy, 27 June 2023

The NAUTILOS project, in collaboration with the Ocean Race Grand Finale, hosted a dynamic Policy Round Table on June 27th in Genova, centered around the topic of NAUTILOS project’s second policy brief, titled “[Supporting Ocean Observations to Address Climate Change](#)”. The event, endorsed by the Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development, underscored the critical importance of cooperation, citizen engagement and ongoing commitment to ocean observation in the context of a changing climate. Experts, policymakers and stakeholders came together to explore the fundamental role of informed decision-making, knowledge sharing and innovative technologies in achieving collective success.

The discussions at the NAUTILOS Policy Round Table resonated with a resounding call for heightened collaboration among diverse stakeholders to address ocean-related challenges. Participants emphasised that robust ocean knowledge requires dedicated observation, data collection and the adoption of innovative technologies. The imperative of building policies and making informed decisions based on the best available knowledge was a recurring theme throughout the event.

Kestutis Sadauskas, representing the European Commission’s Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (EC – DG MARE), highlighted the significance of ocean protection through intelligent strategies and policies build on best available knowledge.

The NAUTILOS project, known for its pioneering work in developing innovative and low-cost ocean observation technologies, was commended for its contribution to effective data collection. Nicolas Segebarth Healthy Oceans and Seas, RTD – DG, EC highlighted that “Ocean observations are typically very expensive, and long-term series are typically not sustained”.

The event demonstrated the power of collaboration and the role of diverse stakeholders in driving solutions for ocean-related challenges. The Policy Round Table of NAUTILOS facilitated valuable insights and discussions, while emphasising the importance of all participants’ commitment to safeguarding our ocean for current and future generations.

The NAUTILOS project developed a [collaborative statement](#) encapsulating the outcomes of the round table discussions. This statement will further underscore the significance of ocean observation, collaboration and innovation in shaping sustainable policies and actions.

To see the full session: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4ydyWY_CfxE&t=705s.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, NAUTILOS plays a crucial role in advancing marine observation and data collection, making significant contributions to various policy areas. The project's comprehensive approach, which includes the development of various sensors and samplers, fosters integration of marine observations from diverse platforms, ultimately leading to more informed and effective policymaking. By addressing critical gaps in data availability related to essential ocean variables (EOVs) and aligning with global and EU initiatives, NAUTILOS is at the forefront of advancing ocean science and sustainability.

The project's involvement in key events is instrumental in disseminating its policy interests and findings to a wider audience. These events serve as knowledge hubs, where NAUTILOS can share insights, technologies, and research outcomes with policymakers and experts. They also facilitate networking and collaboration, enabling the project to align its policy interests with other stakeholders and influence decision makers directly.

NAUTILOS' engagement with targeted events underscores the importance of ocean observation in addressing pressing global challenges, including climate change and sustainable resource management. By advocating for the adoption of FAIR principles and open accessibility of scientific data, NAUTILOS is poised to leave a lasting legacy that aligns with the UN Decade's aspirations for responsible global ocean governance.

The project's participation in these events emphasises the democratisation of science, making marine observation accessible to a broader audience, including citizen scientists. NAUTILOS' commitment to transparency, public engagement, and tailored messaging ensures that its work is relevant to various stakeholders, from policymakers to the general public.

In summary, NAUTILOS' involvement in key events and its dedication to advancing marine observation and data collection contribute significantly to sustainable ocean management, aligning with the goals of SDG 14 and supporting informed decision-making for responsible ocean use. The project's impact extends beyond scientific research, influencing policy frameworks and fostering collaboration among stakeholders to address critical marine challenges.